

In the phytotron fertility was greatly reduced in plants at 38° / 27° C during flowering. Three heat-tolerant rices had higher fertility at 38° / 27° C. This was apparently not related to the fertility at 29° / 21° C, because the heat-susceptible line IR1561-228-3-3 had high fertility at this temperature. Heat-tolerant rices had more pollen grains per stigma than susceptible rices at both temperatures. In tolerant rices, high temperature had little

effect on the number of pollen grains per stigma. In susceptible rices, high temperature greatly reduced the number of pollen grains per stigma (see table).

Pollen shedding on the stigma in field-grown plants showed the same trend as in phytotron-grown plants. The amount of pollen shed on the stigma was not related to the number of pollen grains per anther; two tolerant rices, N22 and IET4658, had significantly less

pollen grains per anther than the other lines.

It appears that the amount of pollen shed on the stigma is related to the time of anther dehiscence in relation to filament elongation. This trait, which distinguishes heat-tolerant from heat-susceptible rices, is expressed under field conditions even in the absence of high temperature. ■

Pest management and control DISEASES

Rice bacterial blight status in the Punjab, India

G. L. Raina, pathologist; G. S. Sidhu, senior breeder; and P. K. Saini, research associate, Punjab Agricultural University, Rice Research Station, Kapurthala, Punjab, India

Bacterial blight (BB) caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* has been known to occur in Punjab State of India since the 1940s. The disease, first observed in Gurdaspur district, was called *purarh* or *pansukh* in the local language, which means blighting or leaf-drying. It was considered to be due to some physiological disorder, and only in 1965 was its etiology established.

BB has been found to appear every year in varying degrees in different areas. During 1980 kharif (dry season), BB assumed an epiphytotic form and caused considerable yield loss throughout the state, in some areas as high as 60-70%. The kresak phase of the disease was also recorded in some fields for the first time.

Increase in BB incidence and severity may be attributed to higher nitrogen applications, very early transplanting, and conducive macro- and microclimatic conditions. The possibility of pathogenic variability also exists.

In the Punjab, the rice season lasts from May to October. Because almost all rice straw is burnt in the fields, there does not seem to be any chance for the bacterium to be carried over to the next crop season through infected rice straw. The possibility of pathogen survival in

Incidence of bacterial blight in Punjab, India.

Year	BB incidence
1975	Moderate to severe
1976	Low to severe
1977	Low to severe
1978	Low to severe
1979	Moderate to severe
1980	Severe

the stubble of infected plants is not ruled out, although harvested rice fields are immediately replanted to wheat.

The speculation is that BB bacterium carries over to the next crop season through infected seed. It is also possible that the pathogen survives in the rhizosphere of wheat and other nonhost plants during winter. Studies are being initiated to identify the source of carry-over. Studies on variability also are in progress. Some resistant donors have been identified and are being used in the breeding program. Progeny will be screened under artificial inoculation conditions. Attempts are being made to develop differentials and to test bacterial isolates from all over the state.

In vitro inhibition of rice fungal pathogens by extracts from higher plants

V. Damodaram Naidu and V. T. John, All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, India

Leaves of *Polyalthia longifolia*, *Parthenium hysterophorus*, and *Cymbopogon* sp. were macerated. The aqueous

extracts were mixed at varying concentrations with potato dextrose agar and tested for antifungal activity by poison-food technique. Rhizomes of *Zingiber officinale* (ginger) and *Curcuma longa* (turmeric) were also tested for antifungal activity. Fungal pathogens tested were *Rhizoctonia solani*, *Sclerotium oryzae*, *Sclerotium rolfsii*, *Acrocyndrium oryzae*, *Helminthosporium oryzae*, and *Pyricularia oryzae*.

Extracts from plants inhibited the growth of most fungal pathogens tested. The growth inhibition was greater in *R. solani* and *S. oryzae* than in other pathogens.

Extracts from *Azadirachta indica*, *Catharanthus roseus*, *Calotropis gigantea*, *Allium cepa*, *A. sativum*, *Eichhornia crassipes*, and *Clerodendron sp.* showed poor growth inhibition of the fungal pathogens tested. ■

Nilaparvata bakeri transmission of rice ragged stunt virus

T. Morinaka, Tropical Agriculture Research Center, Yatabe, Tsukuba, Ibaraki 305, Japan; D. Chettanachit, M. Putta, A. Parejarearn, and S. Disthaporn. Division of Plant Pathology and Microbiology, Department of Agriculture, Bangkok 9, Thailand

Rice ragged stunt virus transmission abilities of *Nephotettix virescens*, *Recilia dorsalis*, *Sogatella furcifera*, and *Nilaparvata bakeri* were tested. Nymphs of *N. virescens* and adults of *R. dorsalis*